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PHYSICIAN-PEDAGOGICAL SUPERVISION IN THE EDUCATIONAL
AND TRAINING PROCESS OF WEIGHTLIFTERS

A.O. Dakhno, assistant

O.V. Slobodyanyuk, senior lecturer

*M. Ye. Zhukovskiyi National Aerospace University
«Kharkiv Aviation Institute»*

Weightlifting, as the name implies, refers to speed and strength sports requiring incredible efforts from athletes to achieve the highest results. At present in this sport, the volume and intensity of training and competitive and, accordingly, psychological activities of weightlifters reach extremely high values. It is enough to look at the world records in all weight categories, including women, to be convinced in the foregoing. Respectively the question of medical and pedagogical supervision of the training process and also application of certain pharmacological means and various medical and biological methods in the given kind of sports aimed at improvement of sportsmen working capacity and its adaptation to growing physical and psychological activities are of great interest in the modern sports. And indeed, the achievement of high results in weightlifting requires from the body of athletes more and more new levels of adaptation. Nowadays to win a place of honor on the podium becomes not only difficult but also often requires incredible efforts from specialists, those who take a part in the training of weightlifters, coaches, sports doctors, nutritionists, psychologists, as well as massage therapists.

A few years ago leading specialists in sports medicine expressed the idea that athletes have the right to extensive pharmacological support and prevention, equating them to professionals working in harsh conditions: astronauts, miners, special forces, etc.

Achievement of high sports results in modern conditions is possible only with a rigorous system of training, including - selection, planning, providing all kinds of rehabilitation and constant medical control of the athlete's body at all stages of preparation for competitions and analysis of the dynamics of competitive activity. Particular attention should be paid to the human predisposition, as a biological being, to practice a particular sport. In everyday practice, there are cases when athletes train at the same level as masters of sports and do not rise above the second category. This is due to the peculiarities of the body.

Medical and pedagogical observation is carried out by a doctor and a coach together in order to assess the impact on the athlete's body of physical loads, as well as to identify the level of functional readiness and, based on these conclusions, improve the educational and training process. The necessity of such studies is that the level of functional readiness of an athlete can be studied and evaluated in the best way possible under natural conditions of the training process, during the study of specific loads. In the process of medical and pedagogical supervision the level of readiness of a particular athlete to perform a

training program, specific signs of incomplete recovery after physical activities and the development of over fatigue or overexertion are determined, such information allows the trainer to introduce appropriate adjustments into the training process in due time. The efficiency of training of the sportsman depends on how correctly chosen the training means and their measuring in one employment, more volume in a microcycle, between a cycle, etc. Trainer often works blindly if he does not know, what influence on an organism of the sportsman specifies a separate exercise, a series of exercises, separate employment, one training day or a stage. Currently, in order to clarify the impact of physical activities on the athlete's body it is customary to monitor the following training effects:

- terminal;
- deferred;
- cumulative.

The urgent training effect is understood as the changes occurring in the athlete's body immediately during the exercise and in the immediate period of rest.

The delayed training effect means changes in the body in the late phases of recovery, i.e. after training and in the following days.

The cumulative training effect is the changes occurring in the athlete's body over a long period, after training sessions, as a result of the summation of urgent and delayed effects from a large number of individual sessions.

Medical and pedagogical observation is carried out jointly by a doctor and a coach and is the most important form of their joint work. Observation allows you to identify favorable and unfavorable changes in the athlete's body and, if necessary, to individualize the training process.

However, the doctor does not always have the opportunity to participate in medical and pedagogical observations, so the coach himself must have simple but effective research methods and be able to use them competently in their work, both to assess the impact of activities and to guide other issues related to the proper organization of the training process.

The main objectives of medical and pedagogical observation:

- Studying the impact of physical activities on the athlete's body in order to assess their adequacy to the level of his training.
- Determination of the functional state of the athlete's body to assess the level of his functional readiness at different stages of training.
- Evaluation of compliance of applied training means and systems with its tasks and possibilities, in order to improve planning and individualization of educational and training process.
- Evaluation and selection of medical, pedagogical and psychological means and methods aimed at improving recovery processes after physical exertion.
- Evaluation of conditions and organization of training sessions.